

JOHASAM: Journal of Health, Applied Sciences and Management
ISSN: 1597-7085 ISSN (Online): 2756-5343

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6464986

Volume 6 | Issue 1 | 2022

Perceived Impacts of Oil Spillage on the Health and Socio-Economic Activities of the Inhabitants of Ahoada West Local Government Area of Rivers State

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Abstract

The study investigated perceived impacts of oil spillage on the health and socio-economic activities of the inhabitants of Ahoada West L.G.A. of Rivers State. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. A sample size of 500 respondents was used through simple random and purposive sampling technique. The research instrument was analysed using the simple percentage, mean score for research questions and chi-square was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level. The results revealed that oil spillage has significant impacts on the physical and social health of the inhabitants of Ahoada West L.G.A. of Rivers State. Although oil spillage had relationship with the mental health and socio-economic activities, the impacts were not considered to have made some significant difference. The study recommended that government at various levels should be concerned with the implementation of environment protection laws in order to protect the environment and health of the people living in the oil and gas producing communities.

Keywords: perceived, impact, oil spillage, health, socio-economic, activities and inhabitants